

Study	Title	Author	Year	Publishing Vehicles
S1	A Deployment Model to Extend Ethically Aligned AI Implementation Method ECCOLA	Jani Antikainen, Mamia Agbese, Hanna-Kaisa Alanen, Erika Halme, Hannakaisa Isomäki, Marianna Jantunen, Kai-Kristian Kemell, Rebekah Rousi, Heidi Vainio-Pekka, Ville Vakkuri	2021	IEEE 29th International Requirements Engineering Conference
S2	Designing Trustworthy AI: A Human-Machine Teaming Framework to Guide Development	Smith, Carol J.	2019	Presented at AAAI FSS-19: Artificial Intelligence in Government and Public Sector, Arlington, Virginia, USA
S3	Ethically Aligned Design: An empirical evaluation of the RESOLVEDD-strategy in Software and Systems development context	Vakkuri, Ville and Kemell, Kai-Kristian and Abrahamsson, Pekka	2019	45th Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA), pp. 46-50, IEEE
S4	Fairway: A Way to Build Fair ML Software	Chakraborty, Joymallya and Majumder, Suvodeep and Yu, Zhe and Menzies, Tim	2020	Proceedings of the 28th ACM Joint European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering (ESEC/FSE '20), November 8– 13, 2020, Virtual Event, USA. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 12 pages.
S5	POLARIS: A framework to guide the development of Trustworthy AI systems	Baldassarre, Maria Teresa and Gigante, Domenico and Kalinowski, Marcos and Ragone, Azzurra	2024	Conference on AI Engineering Software Engineering for AI (CAIN 2024), April 14--15, 2024, Lisbon, Portugal
S6	IEEE 7010: A New Standard for Assessing the Well-being Implications of Artificial Intelligence	Schiff, Daniel and Ayesh, Aladdin and Musikanski, Laura and Havens, John C.	2020	2020 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)
S7	Cui Bono? Software Professionals Should Always Ask "Who Benefits?"	Gotterbarn, Donald and Miller, Keith W.	2024	Computer (Volume: 57, Issue: 2, February 2024)
S8	Developing Responsible Chatbots for Financial Services: A Pattern-Oriented Responsible AI Engineering Approach	Lu, Qinghua and Luo, Yuxiu and Zhu, Liming and Tang, Mingjian and Xu, Xiwei and Whittle, Jon	2023	IEEE Intelligent Systems (Volume: 38, Issue: 6, Nov.-Dec. 2023)
S9	Ethical Considerations of Bias and Fairness in AI Models	Verma, Sarvachan and Paliwal, Neha and Yadav, Kanchan and Vashist, P. C.	2024	2024 2nd International Conference on Disruptive Technologies (ICDT)
S10	Integrating Fairness in the Software Design Process: An Interview Study With HCI and ML Experts	Ryan, Seamus and Nadal, Camille and Doherty, Gavin	2023	IEEE Access (Volume: 11)
S11	Toward Accountable and Explainable Artificial Intelligence Part Two: The Framework Implementation	J. Vice and M. M. Khan	2022	IEEE Access (Volume: 10)

S12	A Multimodal Installation Exploring Gender Bias in Artificial Intelligence	Dobрева, Mihaela and Rukavina, Tea and Stamou, Vivian and Vidaki, Anastasia Nefeli and Zacharopoulou, Lida	2023	Antona, M., Stephanidis, C. (eds) Universal Access in Human-Computer Interaction. HCII 2023.
S13	A responsible AI framework: pipeline contextualisation	Vyhmeister, Eduardo and Castane, Gabriel and Östberg, P.-O. and Thevenin, Simon	2023	AI Ethics 3, 175–197 (2023)
S14	A System Framework for Personalized and Transparent Data-Driven Decisions	Oppold, Sarah and Herschel, Melanie	2020	Dustdar, S., Yu, E., Salinesi, C., Rieu, D., Pant, V. (eds) Advanced Information Systems Engineering. CAiSE 2020. Lecture Notes in Computer Science(), vol 12127. Springer, Cham.
S15	Addressing Human Factors and Ethics in the design of 'Future Work' and Intelligent Systems for use in Financial Services - person centered operations, Intelligent Work & the Triple Bottom Line	Cahill, Joan and Howard, Vivienne and Huang, Yufei and Ye, Junchi and Ralph, Stephen and Dillon, Aidan	2021	Digital Human Modeling and Applications in Health, Safety, Ergonomics and Risk Management. Human Body, Motion and Behavior: 12th International Conference, DHM 2021, Held as Part of the 23rd HCI International Conference, HCII 2021, Virtual Event, July 24–29, 2021, Proceedings, Part I.
S16	An ontology-based approach to engineering ethicality requirements	Guizzardi, Renata and Amaral, Glenda and Guizzardi, Giancarlo and Mylopoulos, John	2023	Softw Syst Model 22, 1897–1923 (2023).
S17	Artificial Intelligence Regulation: a framework for governance	de Almeida, Patricia Gomes Rêgo and dos Santos, Carlos Denner and Farias, Josivania Silva	2021	Ethics Inf Technol 23, 505–525 (2021).
S18	Auditing large language models: a three-layered approach	Mökander, Jakob and Schuett, Jonas and Kirk, Hannah Rose and Floridi, Luciano	2023	AI Ethics (2023).
S19	Data science ethical considerations: a systematic literature review and proposed project framework	Saltz, Jeffrey S. and Dewar, Neil	2019	Ethics Inf Technol 21, 197–208 (2019).
S20	Eliciting Ethicality Requirements Using the Ontology-Based Requirements Engineering Method	Guizzardi, Renata and Amaral, Glenda and Guizzardi, Giancarlo and Mylopoulos, John	2022	Augusto, A., Gill, A., Bork, D., Nurcan, S., Reinhartz-Berger, I., Schmidt, R. (eds) Enterprise, Business-Process and Information Systems Modeling. BPMDS EMMSAD 2022 2022. Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing, vol 450. Springer, Cham.
S21	Ethics by design for artificial intelligence	Brey, Philip and Dainow, Brandt	2023	AI Ethics (2023).
S22	Explainable software systems: from requirements analysis to system evaluation	Chazette, Larissa and Brunotte, Wasja and Speith, Timo	2022	Requirements Eng 27, 457–487 (2022).

S23	From AI ethics principles to data science practice: a reflection and a gap analysis based on recent frameworks and practical experience	Georgieva, Ilina and Lazo, Claudio and Timan, Tjerk and van Veenstra, Anne Fleur	2022	AI Ethics 2, 697–711 (2022).
S24	From the ground up: developing a practical ethical methodology for integrating AI into industry	Anderson, Marc M. and Fort, Karèn	2023	AI & Soc 38, 631–645 (2023).
S25	Guiding Socio-Technical Reflection of Ethical Principles in TEL Software Development: The SREP Framework	Dennerlein, Sebastian and Wolf-Brenner, Christof and Gutounig, Robert and Schweiger, Stefan and Pammer-Schindler, Viktoria	2020	Alario-Hoyos, C., Rodríguez-Triana, M.J., Scheffel, M., Arnedillo-Sánchez, I., Dennerlein, S.M. (eds) Addressing Global Challenges and Quality Education. EC-TEL 2020. Lecture Notes in Computer Science(), vol 12315. Springer, Cham.
S26	How to Write Ethical User Stories? Impacts of the ECCOLA Method	Halme, Erika and Vakkuri, Ville and Kultanen, Joni and Jantunen, Marianna and Kemell, Kai-Kristian and Rousi, Rebekah and Abrahamsson, Pekka	2021	Gregory, P., Lassenius, C., Wang, X., Kruchten, P. (eds) Agile Processes in Software Engineering and Extreme Programming. XP 2021. Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing, vol 419. Springer, Cham.
S27	Implementing AI Ethics in Practice: An Empirical Evaluation of the RESOLVEDD Strategy	Vakkuri, Ville and Kemell, Kai-Kristian	2019	Hyrnsalmi, S., Suoranta, M., Nguyen-Duc, A., Tyrväinen, P., Abrahamsson, P. (eds) Software Business. ICSOB 2019. Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing, vol 370. Springer, Cham.
S28	Operationalising AI ethics through the agile software development lifecycle: a case study of AI-enabled mobile health applications	Amugongo, Lameck Mbangula and Kriebitz, Alexander and Boch, Auxane and Lütge, Christoph	2023	AI Ethics (2023).
S29	Operationalising ethics in artificial intelligence for healthcare: a framework for AI developers	Solanki, Pravik and Grundy, John and Hussain, Waqar	2023	AI Ethics 3, 223–240 (2023).
S30	Policy advice and best practices on bias and fairness in AI	Alvarez, Jose M. and Colmenarejo, Alejandra Bringas and Elobaid, Alaa and Fabbrizzi, Simone and Fahimi, Miriam and Ferrara, Antonio and Ghodsi, Siamak and Mougan, Carlos and Papageorgiou, Ioanna and Reyer, Paula and Russo, Mayra and Scott, Kristen M. and State, Laura and Zhao, Xuan and Ruggieri, Salvatore	2024	Ethics Inf Technol 26, 31 (2024).

S31	Rethinking Personas for Fairness: Algorithmic Transparency and Accountability in Data-Driven Personas	Salminen, Joni and Jung, Soon-gyo and Chowdhury, Shammur A. and Jansen, Bernard J.	2020	Degen, H., Reinerman-Jones, L. (eds) Artificial Intelligence in HCI. HCII 2020. Lecture Notes in Computer Science(), vol 12217. Springer, Cham.
S32	Risk as a driver for AI framework development on manufacturing	Vyhmeister, Eduardo and Gonzalez-Castane, Gabriel and Östberg, P.-O.	2023	AI Ethics 3, 155–174 (2023).
S33	TAI-PRM: trustworthy AI—project risk management framework towards Industry 5.0	Vyhmeister, Eduardo and Castane, Gabriel G.	2024	AI Ethics (2024).
S34	The cyclical ethical effects of using artificial intelligence in education	Dieterle, Edward and Dede, Chris and Walker, Michael	2024	AI & Soc 39, 633–643 (2024).
S35	The Road Less Taken: Pathways to Ethical and Responsible Technologies	Winter, Susan	2024	Werthner, H., et al. Introduction to Digital Humanism. Springer, Cham.
S36	They shall be fair, transparent, and robust: auditing learning analytics systems	Simbeck, Katharina	2024	AI Ethics 4, 555–571 (2024)
S37	Towards fair machine learning using combinatorial methods	Saraswat, Anant and Pal, Manjish and Pokhriyal, Subham and Abhishek, Kumar	2023	Evol. Intel. 16, 903–916 (2023).
S38	A conceptual framework for AI system development and sustainable social equality	Chen, Lucien Yen-Hao	2020	2020 IEEE / ITU International Conference on Artificial Intelligence for Good (AI4G) (2020): 101-106.
S39	A framework for applying ethics-by-design to decision support systems for emergency management	Nussbaumer, A., Pope, A., & Neville, K.	2023	Information Systems Journal, 33(1), 34–55.
S40	A Framework for Systematically Applying Humanistic Ethics when Using AI as a Design Material	Dent, Kyle & Dumond, Richelle & Kuniavsky, Mike	2019	Temes de Disseny. 178-197.
S41	A Maturity Model for Trustworthy AI Software Development	Cho, Seunghwan, Ingyu Kim, Jinhan Kim, Honguk Woo, and Wanseon Shin	2023	Applied Sciences 13, no. 8: 4771.
S42	A step toward building a unified framework for managing AI bias	Rana SA, Azizul ZH, Awan AA	2023	PeerJ Computer Science 9:e1630
S43	A Toolkit to Enable the Design of Trustworthy AI	Schmager, S., Sousa, S.	2021	HCI International 2021 - Late Breaking Papers: Multimodality, eXtended Reality, and Artificial Intelligence. HCII 2021. Lecture Notes in Computer Science(), vol 13095. Springer, Cham.
S44	AI Ethics: An Empirical Study on the Views of Practitioners and Lawmakers	Arif Ali Khan; Muhammad Azeem Akbar; Mahdi Fahmideh; Peng Liang; Muhammad Waseem; Aakash Ahmad	2023	IEEE Transactions on Computational Social Systems, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 2971-2984, Dec. 2023

S45	An Agile Framework for Trustworthy AI	van Belkom, Rudy & Leijnen, Stefan & Aldewereld, Huib & Bijvank, Roland & Ossewaarde, Roelant	2020	ECAI 2020
S46	Building a Maturity Model for Developing Ethically Aligned AI Systems	Marianna Jantunen, Erika Halme, Ville Vakkuri, Kai-Kristian Kemell, Rebekah Rousi, Tommi Mikkonen, Anh Nguyen Duc, and Pekka Abrahamsson	2021	Selected Papers of the IRIS, Issue Nr 12 (2021).
S47	Centring dignity in algorithm development: testing a Dignity Lens	Lorenn P. Ruster, Paola Oliva-Altamirano, and Katherine A. Daniell	2023	Proceedings of the 34th Australian Conference on Human-Computer Interaction (OzCHI '22). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 1–8.
S48	Challenges of responsible AI in practice: scoping review and recommended actions	Malak Sadek, Emma Kallina, Thomas Bohné, Céline Mougnot, Rafael A. Calvo & Stephen Cave	2024	AI & Soc (2024).
S49	Conceptual Foundations on Debiasing for Machine Learning-Based Software	Schmitt, Anuschka & Walser, Maximilian & Fahse, Tobias	2022	International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS) 2022
S50	Context-Based Patterns in Machine Learning Bias and Fairness Metrics: A Sensitive Attributes-Based Approach	Tiago Palma Pagano, Rafael B. Loureiro, Fernanda V.N. Lisboa, Gustavo O.R. Cruz, Rodrigo M. Peixoto, Guilherme A. de Sousa Guimarães, Ewerton L.S. Oliveira, Ingrid Winkler and Erick Giovanni Sperandio Nascimento	2023	Big Data and Cognitive Computing, 7(1).
S51	Design Science Research and Designing Ethical Guidelines for the SHAPES AI Developers	Nevanperä, Minna & Rajamäki, Jyri & Helin, Jaakko	2021	Procedia Computer Science
S52	ECCOLA — A method for implementing ethically aligned AI systems	Vakkuri, Ville & Kemell, Kai-Kristian & Jantunen, Marianna & Halme, Erika & Abrahamsson, Pekka	2021	Journal of Systems and Software
S53	Ethical User stories Industrial study	Halme, Erika & Agbese, Mamia & Antikainen, Jani & Alanen, Hanna-Kaisa & Jantunen, Marianna & Khan, Arif & Kemell, Kai-Kristian & Vakkuri, Ville & Abrahamsson, Pekka	2022	REFSQ-2022 Workshops
S54	Expanding Explainability: Towards Social Transparency in AI systems	Upol Ehsan, Q. Vera Liao, Michael Muller, Mark O. Riedl, and Justin D. Weisz	2021	CHI '21: Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems
S55	Exploring the ethical implications of business analytics with a business ethics canvas	Vidgen, Richard & Hindle, Giles & Randolph, Ian	2020	European Journal of Operational Research, Elsevier, vol. 281(3), pages 491-501.

S56	Governance by Glass-Box: Implementing Transparent Moral Bounds for AI Behaviour	Aler Tubella, Andrea & Theodorou, Andreas & Dignum, Frank & Dignum, Virginia	2019	International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence (IJCAI) 2019
S57	Governance in Ethical and Trustworthy AI Systems: Extension of the ECCOLA Method for AI Ethics Governance Using GARP	Agbese, Mamia & Alanen, Hanna-Kaisa & Antikainen, Jani & Erika, Halme & Isomaki, Hannakaisa & Jantunen, Marianna & Kemell, Kai-Kristian & Rousi, Rebekah & Vainio-Pekka, Heidi & Vakkur, Ville	2023	e-Informatica Software Engineering Journal.
S58	Making ethics practical: User stories as a way of implementing ethical consideration in Software Engineering	Erika Halme, Marianna Jantunen, Ville Vakkuri, Kai-Kristian Kemell, and Pekka Abrahamsson	2024	Inf. Softw. Technol. 167, C (Mar 2024)
S59	Multi-objective Feature Attribution Explanation For Explainable Machine Learning	Ziming Wang, Changwu Huang, Yun Li, and Xin Yao	2024	ACM Trans. Evol. Learn. Optim. 4, 1, Article 2 (March 2024)
S60	Norm Deviation in Multiagent Systems: A Foundation for Responsible Autonomy	SINGH, Amika M.; SINGH, Munindar P	2023	Proceedings of the Thirty-Second International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence
S61	Overview of transparency and inspectability mechanisms to achieve accountability of artificial intelligence systems	Hauer, Marc & Krafft, Tobias & Zweig, Katharina	2023	Data & Policy
S62	Prototyping Ethics-As-Practice: A Framework For Designing Data-Driven Product Service Systems	Sonja Rattay	2023	Companion Publication of the 2023 ACM Designing Interactive Systems Conference (DIS '23 Companion)
S63	Reliability Testing for Natural Language Processing Systems	TAN, Samson; JOTY, Shafiq; BAXTER, Kathy; TAEIHAGH, Araz; BENNETT, Gregory A.; KAN, Min-Yen	2021	Accepted to ACL-IJCNLP 2021 (main conference)
S64	The Need for an Enhanced Process Methodology for Ethical Data Science Projects	S. Lahiri and J. Saltz	2023	IEEE International Symposium on Ethics in Engineering, Science, and Technology (ETHICS), West Lafayette, IN, USA, 2023, pp. 01-05
S65	Toward best practices in embedded ethics: Suggestions for interdisciplinary technology development	Daniel W. Tigard, Maximilian Braun, Svenja Breuer, Konstantin Ritt, Amelia Fiske, Stuart McLennan, and Alena Buyx	2023	Robotics and Autonomous Systems
S66	Value-Based Engineering With IEEE 7000	S. Spiekermann and T. Winkler	2022	IEEE Technology and Society Magazine, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 71-80, Sept. 2022
S67	A Computational Framework for Human Values	Nardine Osman and Mark d'Inverno	2024	Proceedings of the 23rd International Conference on Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems (AAMAS '24)
S68	A Mulching Proposal Analysing and Improving an Algorithmic System for Turning the Elderly into High-Nutrient Slurry	Os Keyes, Jevan Hutson, and Meredith Durbin	2019	Extended Abstracts of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI EA '19). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Paper alt06, 1–11.

S69	A Semiotics-based epistemic tool to reason about ethical issues in digital technology design and development	Simone Diniz Junqueira Barbosa, Gabriel Diniz Junqueira Barbosa, Clarisse Sieckenius de Souza, and Carla Faria Leitão	2021	Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '21). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 363–374.
S70	AI Regulation Is (not) All You Need	Laura Lucaj, Patrick van der Smagt, Djalel Benbouzid	2023	Proceedings of the 2023 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '23).
S71	Bridging the Gap Between Ethics and Practice: Guidelines for Reliable, Safe, and Trustworthy Human-centered AI Systems	Ben Shneiderman	2020	ACM Trans. Interact. Intell. Syst. 10, 4, Article 26 (December 2020), 31 pages
S72	Building and Auditing Fair Algorithms: A Case Study in Candidate Screening	Christo Wilson, Avijit Ghosh, Shan Jiang, Alan Mislove, Lewis Baker, Janelle Szary, Kelly Trindel, and Frida Polli	2021	Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '21)
S73	Closing the AI Accountability Gap: Defining an End-to-End Framework for Internal Algorithmic	Inioluwa Deborah Raji, Andrew Smart, Rebecca N. White, Margaret Mitchell, Timnit Gebru, Ben Hutchinson, Jamila Smith-Loud, Daniel Theron, and Parker Barnes	2020	Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAT* '20)
S74	Co-Designing Checklists to Understand Organizational Challenges and Opportunities around Fairness in AI	Michael A. Madaio, Luke Stark, Jennifer Wortman Vaughan, and Hanna Wallach	2020	Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '20)
S75	Confronting Abusive Language Online: A Survey from the Ethical and Human Rights Perspective	Svetlana Kiritchenko, Isar Nejadgholi, and Kathleen C. Fraser	2021	Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research, Volume 71
S76	Data Ethics Emergency Drill: A Toolbox for Discussing Responsible AI for Industry Teams	Vanessa Aisyahsari Hanschke, Dylan Rees, Merve Alanyali, David Hopkinson, and Paul Marshall	2024	Proceedings of the 2024 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '24)
S77	Dual Cognitive UXD and Explainable AI	Karen Cham, Raida Shakiry, and Carl Yates	2021	Journal of Usability Studies, Volume 17, Issue 1
S78	Experiences with Improving the Transparency of AI Models and Services	Michael Hind, Stephanie Houde, Jacquelyn Martino, Aleksandra Mojsilovic, David Piorkowski, John Richards, and Kush R. Varshney	2020	Extended Abstracts of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI EA '20)
S79	Exploring How Machine Learning Practitioners (Try To) Use Fairness Toolkits	Wesley Hanwen Deng, Manish Nagireddy, Michelle Seng Ah Lee, Jatinder Singh, Zhiwei Steven Wu, Kenneth Holstein, and Haiyi Zhu	2022	Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '22)
S80	How Can We Develop Explainable Systems? Insights from a Literature Review and an Interview Study	Larissa Chazette, Jil Klünder, Merve Balci, and Kurt Schneider	2022	Proceedings of the International Conference on Software and System Processes and International Conference on Global Software Engineering (ICSSP '22)

S81	Implementing AI Ethics: Making Sense of the Ethical Requirements	Mamia Agbese, Rahul Mohanani, Arif Khan, and Pekka Abrahamsson	2023	Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering (EASE '23)
S82	Introducing Algorithmic Bias Considerations in an Introductory CS Course	Marguerite Doman and Chlotia Garrison	2021	Journal of Computing Sciences in Colleges, Volume 37, Issue 5
S83	Investigating How Practitioners Use Human-AI Guidelines: A Case Study on the People + AI Guidebook	Nur Yildirim, Mahima Pushkarna, Nitesh Goyal, Martin Wattenberg, and Fernanda Viégas	2023	Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '23)
S84	Investigating the Extended Metacommunication Template: How a semiotic tool may encourage reflective ethical practice in the development of machine learning systems	Gabriel Diniz Junqueira Barbosa, José Luiz Nunes, Clarisse Sieckenius De Souza, and Simone Diniz Junqueira Barbosa	2024	Proceedings of the XXII Brazilian Symposium on Human Factors in Computing Systems (IHC '23)
S85	Is a Seat at the Table Enough? Engaging Teachers and Students in Dataset Specification for ML in Education	Mei Tan, Hansol Lee, Dakuo Wang, and Hari Subramonyam	2024	Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction, Volume 8, Issue CSCW1
S86	Navigating the Limits of AI Explainability: Designing for Novice Technology Users in Low-Resource Settings	Chinasa T. Okolo	2023	Proceedings of the 2023 AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society (AIES '23)
S87	Outlining Traceability: A Principle for Operationalizing Accountability in Computing Systems	Joshua A. Kroll	2021	Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '21)
S88	Prosocial Norm Emergence in Multi-agent Systems	Mehdi Mashayekhi, Nirav Ajmeri, George F. List, and Munindar P. Singh	2022	ACM Transactions on Autonomous and Adaptive Systems (TAAS), Volume 17, Issue 1-2
S89	Reflexive Design for Fairness and Other Human Values in Formal Models	Benjamin Fish and Luke Stark	2021	Proceedings of the 2021 AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society (AIES '21)
S90	Regulating Artificial Intelligence: A Technology Regulator's Perspective	Joshua Ellul, Gordon Pace, Stephen McCarthy, Trevor Sammut, Juanita Brockdorff, and Matthew Scerri	2021	Proceedings of the Eighteenth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Law (ICAIL '21)
S91	Responsible AI Pattern Catalogue: A Collection of Best Practices for AI Governance and Engineering	Qinghua Lu, Liming Zhu, Xiwei Xu, Jon Whittle, Didar Zowghi, and Aurelie Jacquet	2024	ACM Computing Surveys, Volume 56, Issue 7
S92	Saving Face: Investigating the Ethical Concerns of Facial Recognition Auditing	Inioluwa Deborah Raji, Timnit Gebru, Margaret Mitchell, Joy Buolamwini, Joonseok Lee, and Emily Denton	2020	Proceedings of the AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society (AIES '20)
S93	Software engineering for Responsible AI: An empirical study and operationalised patterns	Qinghua Lu, Liming Zhu, Xiwei Xu, Jon Whittle, David Douglas, and Conrad Sanderson	2022	Proceedings of the 44th International Conference on Software Engineering: Software Engineering in Practice (ICSE-SEIP '22)

S94	Software Engineering Methods for Responsible Artificial Intelligence	Zahoor UI Islam	2021	Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Autonomous Agents and MultiAgent Systems (AAMAS '21)
S95	Soliciting Stakeholders' Fairness Notions in Child Maltreatment Predictive Systems	Hao-Fei Cheng, Logan Stapleton, Ruiqi Wang, Paige Bullock, Alexandra Chouldechova, Zhiwei Steven Wu, and Haiyi Zhu	2021	Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '21)
S96	The A.I. Pandora: Linking Ethically-challenged Technical Outputs to Prospective Policy Approaches	Robert J. Domanski	2019	Proceedings of the 20th Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research (dg.o '19)
S97	Tinker, Tailor, Configure, Customize: The Articulation Work of Contextualizing an AI Fairness Checklist	Michael A. Madaio, Jingya Chen, Hanna Wallach, and Jennifer Wortman Vaughan	2024	Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction, Volume 8, Issue CSCW1
S98	Towards a multi-stakeholder value-based assessment framework for algorithmic systems	Mireia Yurrita, Dave Murray-Rust, Agathe Balayn, and Alessandro Bozzon	2022	Proceedings of the 2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '22)
S99	TOWARDS A ROADMAP ON SOFTWARE ENGINEERING FOR RESPONSIBLE AI	Qinghua Lu, Liming Zhu, Xiwei Xu, Jon Whittle, and Zhenchang Xing	2022	Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on AI Engineering: Software Engineering for AI (CAIN '22)
S100	Understanding Machine Learning Practitioners' Data Documentation Perceptions, Needs, Challenges, and Desiderata	Amy K. Heger, Liz B. Marquis, Mihaela Vorvoreanu, Hanna Wallach, and Jennifer Wortman Vaughan	2022	Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction, Volume 6, Issue CSCW2
S101	Using Model Cards for Ethical Reflection: A Qualitative Exploration	José Luiz Nunes, Gabriel D. J. Barbosa, Clarisse Sieckenius de Souza, Helio Lopes, and Simone D. J. Barbosa	2022	Proceedings of the 21st Brazilian Symposium on Human Factors in Computing Systems (IHC '22)
S102	Where Responsible AI meets Reality: Practitioner Perspectives on Enablers for Shifting Organizational Practices	Bogdana Rakova, Jingying Yang, Henriette Cramer, and Rumman Chowdhury	2021	Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction, Volume 5, Issue CSCW1